

DRAMATIC CHILD-HERO: EXISTENCE, INTERRELATION AND DIFFERENTIATION OF AESTHETIC PHENOMENA

Mavlyanova Nigina Erkinovna

Independent researcher,
Bukhara State University
genius18051992@mail.ru

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Abstract. Authors of world literature have addressed the image of a child and the theme of childhood for many centuries, saying that "in the historical and literary depiction of childhood, like other periods of human development, there is a complex of aesthetic values strengthened by cultural development, connected with cultural tradition and social has a variable character under the influence of trends. Changing and acquiring new functions, the artistic image of a child embodied in literature is the key to understanding what a child "is" in the entire historical process.

Key words. Drama, play, child hero, image, aesthetic phenomenon, psychological analysis.

Introduction. The theme of childhood occupies a particularly stable position in children's characters and fiction, which is mainly due to its constant interaction with the fantastic field of extratextual reality. Researcher of children's literature P. Hunt writes about this: "children's books have an interesting relationship with childhood and are a very unreliable reference of childhood. Childhood as depicted in children's literature may represent a model of what adults think or want it to be; or portrays the image that adults want. It is difficult to imagine children's literature that cannot control the audience. At the same time, it is unfair to consider children's themes and child characters as only children's literature and for children, as a result of which there is a problem of children's works.

There are various concepts describing the principles and criteria for distinguishing children's and adult literature, which are presented in the works of scientists such as H.Evers, M.Mick, M.Stiles, M.Nikolaeva, I.Arzamasseva, M.Granby. The most successful concept of children's literature, in our opinion, is the scheme of H. Evers, that is, the ratio of the core and the periphery, where the core is a collection of works created specifically for children and included in the scope of children's reading (targeted children's literature), the peripheral area is made up of artistic texts. These texts are not examples of targeted children's

literature, but are of interest to child readers, or, conversely, are aimed at a children's audience, but this audience does not need them.

Analysis. The interpretation of the term "drama with children's participation" presented in the collective monograph "Canadian Children's Drama and Theater" does not contradict the concept described above, its authors use children's dramas in the sense of "a valuable and important genre of children's literature". According to D. Davis, children's dramas are specially created for staging by children's groups, aimed at children's audiences and children's readers, and have a strong educational and educational potential, because when a child is reading a play or a role in a play when he plays, he "forgets the difference between life and play, he becomes a participant in the action, not an observer."

The authors of the presented concepts focus on the following:

- a practical-oriented characteristic of creative drama;
- the importance of creating dramas for children;
- using them in the educational process of the young generation;
- didactic-game orientation;
- they consider dramatic works and performances created for children as an integral part of the dramatic genre.

According to the researchers of the effectiveness of drama, "Dramatic work shows the unique characteristics of childhood in general. "Young children imitate the behavior and actions of older children and parents", so it is natural for children to imitate not only people in the environment, but also dramatic characters.

In contrast to the above-mentioned approaches, the researcher S. Greenhalgh in the essay "Drama" distinguishes children's drama as a separate genre, mentions dramas created with the participation of children's characters, and emphasizes that children's drama and children's plays are a phenomenon of children's culture. literature focuses on the phenomenon of drama: says that "comments should be made on the terminology of children's drama". "Creative drama", "stage performance" or "children's play" is understood as an informal visual activity of children (and sometimes their older observers), usually given randomly and improvised, usually without any preliminary script, because it is in children designed for the development of feelings and sensitivity, creative abilities". In addition, according to the researcher, children's drama includes not only plays created by children's groups to be staged in educational institutions, but also theatrical performances in a professional children's theater or a theater

for young audiences, fairy tales, poems, poems included in the scope of children's reading. , the main epic works of children's literature and adult literature are also included (G.H. Andersen's fairy tales, K. Graham's novel "The Wind in the Willows", J. Barrie's trilogy of stories about Peter Pan and the play "Peter Pan", L. Carroll's "Alice in Wonderland" and " "Alice Through the Looking-Glass" dialogue, F.H. Burnett's novel "Little Lord Fauntleroy", A.A. Millen's novels, etc.).

It seems reasonable to us to label plays of this nature as children's dramas. It is noteworthy that scholars studying children's literature tend to define children's drama as a genre, but none of the above-mentioned studies indicate the parameters of such a genre as "children's drama", which indicates a high degree of conditionality in defining children's drama as a special genre of children's literature. can show. Broader than any genre canon in all its forms of existence. At the same time, attempts of scholars to find a controversial sign of this aesthetic phenomenon belonging to the field of children's literature give rise to hypotheses about the nature of children's drama.

The main theoretical and methodological difficulties and contradictions arise in the study of modern drama about children, which, of course, is an aesthetic phenomenon wider than drama as a genre, because dramatic works include children's problems and characters among the actors - children's comedies, tragicomedies, dramas and tragedies. The factor that divides children's plays into a special group is the system of images from dramatic works (the main characters of a child, a teenager or an adult, a child's behavior model, childish character traits or infantilism) and specific features of the conflict: in children's plays, the child's psychological and the emotional world (or infantile adult), the motives of his actions, the relationship between the older and the younger generation, the problems of socialization and integration of the new generation into the "big world", the cultural norms and rules of children's behavior established by adults compliance level. Children's drama has its own palette of child characters ("godly child", "victim child", "spoilt child", "digital child", etc.), which forms a pair with other characters in such a way that the typical social roles of children in the family, school the environment and the circle of peers (child and parent, child and teacher, child and child) are analyzed. In children's drama, the area where conflicts mature and arise is the area traditionally considered as the area of "life activity" of the child (family circle, school and other educational institutions with characteristic features for them, children's groups/temporary children's associations). repeats, virtual dimensions of social

networks, computer games, etc. Children's drama, for example, dramatic texts are often characterized by a special intonation-speech organization (characters' speeches often form children's and teenagers' slang).

Discussion. Another characteristic feature of modern children's drama is the construction of an opposition between childhood and infantilism. If it is revealed by playwrights as a natural period of growth in children's plays, infantilism appears as a destructive phenomenon and is sometimes not connected with the physiological childhood of the hero. Compared to previous eras, the 20th century gave rise to a new type of dramatic heroes - babies who have already passed childhood, but have retained the maturity of spirit and mind. Often in modern dramas, local and foreign dramatists describe child characters as those who have experienced acute attacks of mental autism, are disturbed, do not live in real life, but live in virtual life. However, modern drama, according to N. E. Seibel, "does not actively solve the conflict of generations, the problems of infantilism, the problems of separation - it passively studies the process of evolution of self-awareness of adults. In a personality crisis, he puts the problems of adults on the child.

Most contemporary children's dramas are created as part of youth creative projects (for example, the annual British theater festival Connections) with the participation of well-known playwrights. The purpose of such festivals is to create new performances about childhood and modern children, and the result of the work should be another step towards the understanding of the younger generation by the older generation. Although the plays were originally planned as adult conversations about children, the subjects of the creative studies are often involved in the discussions, resulting in some children's dramas being aimed at child and adolescent audiences. It is characterized by a borderline position between children's and adult literature and its orientation to the masses and the absence of two-level (for children and adults) explanation.

Conclusion. The gradual formation of a child from a passive (dynamic character), from an active character to an actor, showing a unique character and behavior model, makes it possible to belong to one or another type of character. The European dramas of the Enlightenment period and the dramas of the Uzbek Enlightenment period have in common that they focus on the pedagogical and educational component. But the dramatists of this period paid attention to the behavior and character of a non-ideal child, his ignorance and disrespectful attitude towards parents.

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